

SYSTEMATIC INSIGHTS INTO THE EFFECTS OF OBESITY ON MENSTRUAL HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Obesity, a growing global fitness concern, exerts a multifaceted influence on menstrual health. Research has shown obesity can disrupt menstrual cycles, increase the risk of conditions such as polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), besides adversely affect fertility. Menstrual health is a

critical component of overall reproductive and physical well-being, encompassing factors of menstrual cycle regularity. Understanding these relationships is crucial not only for improving health but also for aiding healthcare practitioners, researchers, and policymakers in addressing the increasing prevalence of obesity-related health disputes. Weight reduction has been shown to augment reproductive outcomes by alleviating symptoms of urinary incontinence besides reducing morbidity associated with gynaecological surgery. However, achieving sustained and significant weight loss remains challenging through the current lifestyle besides dietary interventions. Several pharmacological treatment options are available, and emerging evidence highlights the potential benefits of surgical interventions for improving reproductive outcomes in individuals with obesity. Menstrual irregularities and disorders can profoundly affect women's healthcare, public health, quality of life and emotional and reproductive aspirations. As obesity continues its global upward trajectory, it becomes increasingly imperative to address the complex consequences of this epidemic on women's health. Future research efforts are essential to deepen our empathetic of how obesity impacts menstrual health and to develop strategies improve the overall well-being of women worldwide. The consequence helps for future developmental subjective areas like healthcare Implications, reproductive healthpublic health, research gaps, policy and education.

KEYWORDS: Obesity, menstrual polycystic ovary syndrome, reproductive, pharmacological treatment, epidemic, worldwide and healthcare.

INTRODUCTION:

Feminine wellbeing, a vital feature of a lady's general prosperity, assumes a crucial part in her regenerative and physical health^[1] Increasing heftiness rates all over the planet significantly affect female conceptive wellbeing. Youth weight is related with beginning stage of pubescence, feminine inconsistencies during puberty and polycystic ovary disorder. Ladies of regenerative age with high BMIs have a higher gamble of ovulatory issues and will generally answer inadequately to ripeness treatment^[2]

The monthly cycle, normally portrayed by routineness, is an indispensable mark of hormonal equilibrium and regenerative capability. Notwithstanding, for a rising number of ladies around the world, this key part of their wellbeing is being impacted by a worldwide wellbeing plague - corpulence. The complicated transaction among weight and feminine wellbeing has arisen as a subject of significant significance and logical investigation.^[3]

An ordinary monthly cycle is a complex and finely-tuned physiological interaction, represented by a fragile interchange of chemicals, flagging pathways, and criticism components. Notwithstanding, in a period where the worldwide predominance of weight has arrived at pestilence extents, this multifaceted equilibrium is progressively under danger. The connection among stoutness and feminine wellbeing is a subject of developing significance, inciting broad examination and clinical investigation^[4]

Stoutness, portrayed by an over the top gathering of fat tissue, has arrived at disturbing extents all around the world. Its complex effect on wellbeing is indisputable, enveloping a range of constant sicknesses like diabetes, cardiovascular problems, and certain malignant growths. However, past these laid out wellbeing worries, there exists a lesser-investigated component of stoutness' impact - the significant effect it applies on ladies' feminine health^[5]

Stout ladies have been found to have sporadic periods with expanded occurrences of oligomenorrhea or amenorrhea. Inconsistencies in ovulation have likewise been illustrated, and stout ladies have higher paces of miscarriages^[6] Through this deliberate examination, we seek to make a considerable commitment to the more extensive talk encompassing ladies' wellbeing, with a definitive goal of improving the general prosperity and conceptive strength of ladies wrestling with the double difficulties of heftiness and feminine wellbeing. Investigated the different ways weight can influence feminine wellbeing, including the improvement of feminine problems and barrenness, and gives experiences into the basic components. Examined the commonness of oligomenorrhea (rare monthly cycles) and amenorrhea (nonattendance of feminine periods) in everyone and investigates potential gamble factors, including weight. Surveyed meta-examination explicitly centered around the relationship among stoutness and focal corpulence in ladies with PCOS and their effect on feminine and regenerative results. Various examinations have indicated the unpredictable associations among corpulence and feminine wellbeing, yet a thorough combination of this information is lacking^[10] An endeavor has been made through the logical writing, planning to develop an all encompassing comprehension of the effect of heftiness on feminine wellbeing, exploring the complex pathways and collaborations, analyze the basic physiological systems, and fundamentally investigating the ramifications for clinical practice, general wellbeing mediations, and the ID of future exploration needs. By inspecting the perplexing associations among stoutness and feminine wellbeing, this audit looks to illuminate medical care professionals, analysts, and policymakers about the basic ramifications for ladies' conceptive and by and large actual wellbeing. This survey means to explain the diverse impact of stoutness on feminine wellbeing, featuring its job in monthly cycle aggravations, expanded chance of polycystic ovarian and ripeness issues. The survey will likewise address the difficulties in accomplishing supported weight reduction through way of life and dietary measures, investigating the accessible pharmacological and careful treatment choices and underline the significance of tending to heftiness related medical problems in future exploration and strategy making to upgrade ladies' prosperity all around the world. Weight is related with early adolescence and broken uterine dying (Name). Stout young ladies as often as possible enter pubescence at a more youthful age than their typical weight peers^[11]

For sure, the rising predominance of weight in American kids is probably going to be undoubtedly somewhat answerable for the diminishing time of adolescence in the U.S. The mean time of menarche diminished by roughly 3 months in U.S. white young ladies and 5.5 months in

U.S. people of color between the last part of the 1960s and 1990.^[12] Early adolescence can create psychosocial strain in young ladies and their families as they adapt to the social repercussions of early sexual turn of events. As a matter of fact, early pubescence has been demonstrated to be a gamble factor for self-detailed misery in adolescents.^[13] There are a few speculations to make sense of the connection among's BMI and beginning of menses. The basic fat speculation, first set forth by Frisch et al. in 1971, proposes that menarche is set off once a basic degree of largeness is obtained.^[14,15] Leptin might be the connection that characterizes "sufficient degree of bloatedness" and triggers beginning of pubescence. Leptin is a fat-determined chemical that directs energy admission and use. Its focuses ascend with expanding adiposity. Leptin levels additionally ascend with the beginning of adolescence in girls.^[16] Ahima et al. shown that leptin infusion triggers beginning of adolescence in juvenile mice.^[17] Given this finding, it is conceivable that fat youngsters enter pubescence sooner than their typical weight peers attributable to expanded leptin levels set off by bigger volumes of fat tissue. Corpulence keeps on impacting the monthly cycle over the course of life. Postmenarchal overweight ladies frequently experience the ill effects of broken uterine dying coming about because of fringe change of androgens to oestrogens, and adjusted estrogen-progesterone proportions. The constant estrogen-driven multiplication of endometrial tissue prompts endometrial abundance and draining at unpredictable spans.

The capacity of weight reduction and metformin treatment to further develop feminine cyclicality features the job of abundance fat tissue and insulin obstruction in causing Name in corpulent ladies. In a randomized, twofold visually impaired, fake treatment controlled investigation of 143 hefty oligo-or amenorrhoeic ladies with PCOS randomized to get metformin or fake treatment, weight reduction alone related with an improvement in menses.^[18] Probably, weight reduction reestablishes customary feminine capability by diminishing the aromatization of androgens to oestrogens in fat tissue. Some could contend that weight reduction additionally works on feminine capability by expanding insulin responsiveness.

Metformin is likewise a viable treatment for broken uterine dying. Notwithstanding changed androgen levels and estrogen-progesterone proportions, large ladies habitually show some level of insulin obstruction, a component normal for PCOS. Various examinations support the capacity of metformin to reestablish typical menses in ladies with DUB.^[19] In a forthcoming, randomized, twofold visually impaired fake treatment controlled investigation of 45 anovulatory ladies with PCOS randomized to get metformin or fake treatment, just the ladies with insulin obstruction who were treated with metformin showed an improvement in feminine cyclicality (80% in the metformin bunch versus 18% in the fake treatment group).^[20] In that review, enhancements in feminine cyclicality happened freely of weight and hormonal changes. Those discoveries recommend that insulin opposition might be a free supporter of Name in corpulent ladies, separate from the impacts of overabundance fat tissue.

Given the harmful impacts of heftiness on regenerative capability in the two young ladies and ladies, doctors ought to support their patients since early on to keep a typical weight and guidance stout patients that weight reduction might improve their feminine brokenness. Large ladies with insulin obstruction may likewise profit from metformin treatment.

Obesity is a global public health challenge, characterized by an excess accumulation of body fat. Its prevalence has risen dramatically over the past few decades, and it is associated with a wide range of adverse health effects. This comprehensive overview explores the multifaceted impact of obesity on health, covering both physical and psychological consequences, and provides insights into the importance of addressing this critical health issue.

Obesity significantly increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD), including coronary artery disease, stroke, and hypertension. Excess body fat can lead to the accumulation of plaque in arteries (atherosclerosis) and increase the workload on the heart. Additionally, obesity is associated with adverse lipid profiles, such as elevated LDL cholesterol and triglycerides, and reduced levels of HDL cholesterol, all of which contribute to CVD risk.^[21]

DeUgarte CM & Bartolucci AA^[22] investigated the prevalence of insulin resistance, often associated with obesity, in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and its potential impact on menstrual dysfunction. Obesity is a primary risk factor for the development of type 2 diabetes mellitus. Excess fat, particularly visceral fat, disrupts insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism. Over time, this can lead to insulin resistance and the inability of cells to efficiently use glucose, resulting in elevated blood sugar levels.^[23]

Carrying excess weight places additional stress on the musculoskeletal system, leading to conditions like osteoarthritis and lower back pain. Obese individuals are more prone to joint degeneration, and the knees, hips, and spine is particularly vulnerable.^[24]

Obesity is linked to various respiratory issues, including sleep apnea, asthma, and decreased lung function. Excessive fat deposits in the upper airway can obstruct breathing during sleep, leading to sleep apnoea. Obesity-related inflammation can also exacerbate asthma symptoms.^[25]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Population

This study was conducted systematic review and meta-analysis to explore the effects of obesity on menstrual health. We followed the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines to ensure transparency and replicability.^[25-28]

Inclusion Criteria

Studies were included if they:

Examined the relationship between obesity (defined by BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²) and menstrual health outcomes (e.g., menstrual irregularities, amenorrhea, menorrhagia, dysmenorrhea, or hormonal profiles).

Were observational (cross-sectional, case-control, or cohort) or interventional studies.

Exclusion Criteria

Focused on populations with known endocrine disorders unrelated to obesity, such as polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Did not provide quantitative data on menstrual health outcomes. Were reviews, case reports, or conference abstracts^[30].

Literature Search Strategy

A systematic search of electronic databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Embase, was conducted. Boolean operators and truncation symbols were employed to refine the search. Grey literature was searched using Google Scholar and clinical trial registries^[31].

Data Extraction

Two independent reviewers extracted data using a pre-piloted form. Information collected included:

Study characteristics (author, year, study design, sample size).

Participant demographics (age, BMI categories).

Menstrual health outcomes.

Statistical measures (odds ratios, relative risks, p-values).

Discrepancies were resolved through discussion or consultation with a third reviewer.

Quality Assessment

The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) was used to assess the quality of observational studies. Randomized controlled trials (RCTs), if included, were assessed using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool. Studies with a score of ≥ 6 on the NOS were considered high quality^[32].

Ethical Considerations

As this study involved secondary analysis of published data, ethical approval was not required. The study adhered to guidelines for systematic reviews to ensure proper citation and acknowledgment of all sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our collected data explained to the obesity exerts profound impacts on gynecologic health, influencing reproductive and menstrual well-being in women. This section discusses key findings and implications of obesity on menstrual health, highlighting physiological mechanisms and associated health outcomes. Obesity is strongly associated with menstrual irregularities, manifesting in various forms. Women with obesity are at an increased risk of amenorrhea, characterized by the absence of menstruation for several months. Excess adipose tissue disrupts hormonal homeostasis, particularly by altering estrogen and progesterone levels, which are essential for regular menstrual cycles. This condition arises due to hormonal dysregulation caused by excess adiposity, making menstrual tracking challenging and affecting reproductive planning^[33]. Obesity-related hormonal imbalances contribute significantly to menstrual irregularities. Excess fat tissue elevates estrogen levels, disrupting the delicate hormonal

feedback loops regulating ovulation and menstruation. Anovulation is common in women with obesity, leading to irregular or absent menstrual cycles. PCOS, a prevalent endocrine disorder in women closely linked to obesity. Findings indicate hormonal imbalances characteristic of PCOS, leading to irregular cycles, anovulation, and ovarian cyst development. Insulin resistance, a hallmark of obesity, aggravates PCOS symptoms by promoting androgen overproduction. This results in clinical manifestations such as hirsutism, acne, and alopecia^[34]. The irregular ovulatory cycles and poor oocyte quality associated with obesity impair fertility. Women with obesity face: Reduced likelihood of conception due to unpredictable ovulatory patterns. Lower egg quality, necessitating assisted reproductive technologies for successful conception. Women with obesity experience heightened menstrual discomfort, including: Severe menstrual cramps are more prevalent in women with obesity, significantly impacting quality of life^[35]. Heavy menstrual bleeding is common, further exacerbating physical besides emotional distress. Obesity's impact extends beyond menstrual health, contributing to: Increased risk of hormone-dependent cancers, such as endometrial and breast cancers, due to chronic inflammation and estrogen dominance. Psychological effects, including depression, anxiety, and reduced self-esteem, often exacerbated by societal stigmatization. Elevated risk of cardiovascular disease type 2 diabetes, and reduced life expectancy. Adipose tissue serves as an active endocrine organ, producing hormones like leptin and adipokines, which interfere with hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis signaling. Chronic low-grade inflammation, associated with obesity, contributes to hormonal imbalances and ovulatory dysfunction. Mitigating obesity's effects on menstrual health requires a multifactorial approach: Weight management through diet and exercise improves hormonal balance and menstrual regularity. Pharmacological treatments or bariatric surgery may be necessary in severe cases^[36]. Obesity's impact on menstrual health is profound and multifaceted, disrupting hormonal balance, fertility, and overall reproductive well-being. Addressing obesity through targeted interventions is crucial for improving menstrual health and enhancing the quality of life for affected women. Continued research is vital to uncover underlying mechanisms and develop effective strategies for prevention and management. Obesity affects placental development, decreasing its capacity to support fetal growth and increasing the risk of early pregnancy loss. Obesity significantly affects reproductive outcomes, including an increased risk of miscarriage, fertility challenges, and long-term health risks^[37]. Recognizing the mechanisms through which obesity influences pregnancy outcomes allows healthcare providers to offer tailored counseling and interventions. This approach improves the chances of successful pregnancies and mitigates the broader health implications of obesity in women. Obesity significantly affects gynaecologic health, influencing menstrual regularity, fertility, pelvic floor integrity, surgical outcomes sexual besides psychological^[38]. Effective management strategies, including lifestyle changes, medical interventions, and the integration of traditional remedies, can alleviate these challenges and enhance the overall quality of life for women affected by

obesity. Addressing these issues requires early intervention and sustained commitment from healthcare providers and patients alike.

CONCLUSION

This systematic analysis sought to unravel the intricate connections between obesity and menstrual health, delving into the wealth of research available to provide a comprehensive overview of the topic. Through a rigorous examination of existing literature, this review was aimed to shed light on the mechanisms by which obesity affects the menstrual cycle, menstrual disorders, and fertility in women. The review also tried to identify trends, variations, and gaps in the current body of knowledge, offering insights that can inform clinical practice, public health strategies, and future research endeavours^[39]. In conclusion, obesity exerts a multifaceted and far-reaching impact on menstrual health in women. It disrupts regular menstrual cycles, exacerbates conditions like PCOS, hampers fertility, and increases the burden of menstrual pain and discomfort. Understanding and addressing these associations are crucial not only for improving individual well-being but also for informing healthcare strategies and interventions aimed at mitigating the effects of obesity on women's reproductive health^[40].

Managing obesity-induced menstrual disorders involves a multi-faceted approach, including weight management, hormonal therapy, surgical interventions, and addressing associated health conditions. Personalized treatment plans, regular follow-up, and ongoing support are essential to improving menstrual health and overall well-being in individuals affected by these disorders^[41].

Moreover, exploring the impact of obesity on menstrual health through a systematic analysis is not only academically relevant but also holds significant practical implications for women's healthcare, public health, woman's quality of life, emotional well-being, and reproductive aspirations. As obesity rates continue to rise globally, the need to address the consequences of this epidemic on women's health becomes increasingly urgent on the intricate consequences of this epidemic on women's health^[42].

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES:

1. Marcy ML, Alicia A. Impact of obesity on women's health. *Fertil Steril*, 2009; 91(5): 144-148.

2. Carreau AM, Baillargeon J, Laing F. Obesity, and the polycystic ovary syndrome. *Curr Opin Endocrinol Diabetes Obes*, 2010; 17(6): 501-507.
3. Flegal K M, Kruszon-Moran D, Carroll MD, Fryar CD, Ogden CL. Trends in obesity among adults in the United States, 2005 to 2014. *JAMA*, 2016; 315(21): 2284-2291.
4. Pandey S, Bhattacharya S. Impact of obesity on gynaecology. *Women's Health*, 2010; 6(1): 107–117.
5. Khalida I. The effects of obesity on the menstrual cycle. *Curr Probl Pediatr Adolesc Health Care*, 2022; 52: 101241.
6. Rosenfield RL, Ehrmann DA. The pathogenesis of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS): The hypothesis of PCOS as functional ovarian hyperandrogenism revisited. *Endocrine Rev*, 2016; 37(5): 467-520.
7. Rogers J, Mitchell G. The impact of obesity on menstrual disorders and infertility. *Endocrinol Metab Clin North Am*, 2019; 48(2): 285-296.
8. Bhattacharya SM., Jha A. Prevalence, and risk factors of oligomenorrhea and amenorrhea in a general population. *J Obstet Gynaecol India*, 2010; 60(5): 372-377.
9. Lim SS, Davies MJ, Norman RJ, Moran, L. J. Overweight, obesity and central obesity in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Hum Reprod Update*, 2013; 19(3): 292-309.
10. Moran LJ, Hutchison SK, Norman RJ, Teede HJ. Lifestyle changes in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*, 2011; 7(7): CD007506.
11. Himes JH. Examining the evidence for recent secular changes in the timing of puberty in U.S. children considering increases in the prevalence of obesity, *Mol Cell Endocrinol*, 2006; 254–255: 12-13.
12. Must A, Naumova EN, Phillips, Blum M, Dawson-Hughes B, Rand WM. Childhood overweight and the maturational timing in the development of adult overweight and fatness: the Newton Girls Study and its follow-up. *Pediatr*, 2005; 116: 620-627.
13. Kaltila-Heino R, Kosunen E, Rimpela M. Pubertal timing, sexual behaviour, and self-reported depression in middle adolescence. *J Adolesc*, 2003; 26: 531-545.
14. Frisch RE, Revelle R. Height and weight at menarche and a hypothesis of menarche. *Arch Dis Child*, 1971; 48: 695-70.
15. Frisch RE, McArthur JW. Menstrual cycles: fatness as a determinant of minimum weight for height necessary for their maintenance or onset. *Sci*, 1974; 185: 949-951.
16. Ahemed ML, Ong K, Morrel D, Cox L, Drayer N, Perry L, *et al*. Longitudinal study of leptin concentrations during puberty: sex differences and relationship to changes in body composition. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 1999; 84: 899-905.
17. Ahima RS, Dushay J, Flier SN, Prabakaran D, Flier JS. Leptin accelerates the onset of puberty in normal female mice. *J Clin Invest*, 1997; 99: 391-395.

18. Tang T, Glanville J, Hayden CJ, White D, Barth JH, Balen AH. Combined lifestyle modification and metformin in obese patients with polycystic ovary syndrome. A randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind multicentre study. *Hum Reprod*, 2006; 21: 80-89.
19. Essah PA, Apridonidze T, Iuorno MJ, Nestler JE. Effects of short-term and long-term metformin treatment on menstrual cyclicality in women with polycystic ovary syndrome. *Fertil Steril*, 2006; 86: 230-232.
20. Eisenhardt S, Schwarzmann N, Henschel V, Germeyer A, von Wolff M, Hamann A, *et al*. Early effects of metformin in women with polycystic ovary syndrome: a prospective randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2006; 91: 946-952.
21. Poirier P, Giles TD, Bray GA, Hong Y, Stern JS, Pi-Sunyer FX, Eckel RH. Obesity and cardiovascular disease: pathophysiology, evaluation, and effect of weight loss: an update of the 1997 American Heart Association Scientific Statement on Obesity and Heart Disease from the Obesity Committee of the Council on Nutrition, Physical Activity, and Metabolism. *Circulation*, 2006; 113(6): 898-918.
22. De Ugarte CM, Bartolucci AA. Prevalence of insulin resistance in the polycystic ovary syndrome using the homeostasis model assessment. *Fertil Steril*, 2006, 86(4): 1044-1045.
23. Colditz GA, Willett WC, Rotnitzky A, Manson JE. Weight gain as a risk factor for clinical diabetes mellitus in women. *Ann Int Med*, 1995; 122(7): 481-486.
24. Felson DT, Zhang Y, Anthony JM, Naimark A, Anderson JJ. Weight loss reduces the risk for symptomatic knee osteoarthritis in women. The Framingham Study. *Ann Int Med*, 1992; 116(7): 535-539.
25. Mafort T.T, Rufino R, Costa CH, Lopes AJ. Obesity: systemic and pulmonary complications, biochemical abnormalities, and impairment of lung function. *Multidiscip Respir Med*, 2016; 11(1): 28,
26. Renehan AG, Tyson M, Egger M, Heller R F, Zwahlen M. Body-mass index and incidence of cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective observational studies. *Lancet*, 2008; 371: 569-578.
27. Luppino FS, de Wit LM, Bouvy PF, Stijnen T, Cuijpers P, Penninx BW, Zitman FG. Overweight, obesity, and depression: a systematic review and meta-analysis of longitudinal studies. *Arch Gen Psych*, 2010; 67(3): 220-229.
28. Pasquali R, Patton L, Gambineri A. Obesity and infertility. *Curr Opin Endocrinol Diabetes Obes*, 2007; 14(6): 482-487.
29. Whitlock G, Lewington S, Sherliker P, Clarke R, Emberson J, Halsey J, Peto R. Body-mass index and cause-specific mortality in 900 000 adults: collaborative analyses of 57 prospective studies. *Lancet*, 2009; 373(9669): 1083-1096.
30. Polotsky AJ, Polotsky HN. Metabolic implications of menopause. *Semin Reprod Med*, 2010; 28(5): 426-434.

31. Yildiz BO, Azziz R. Impact of obesity on the risk for polycystic ovary syndrome. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*, 2008; 93(1): 162-168.
32. Bellver J, Pellicer A. Obesity and assisted reproductive technology outcomes. *Reprod Biomed Online*, 2011; 23(6): 720-728.
33. Ju H, Jones M, Mishra GD. The prevalence and risk factors of dysmenorrhea. *Epidemiol Rev*, 2014; 36(1): 104-113.
34. Metwally M, Ong KJ, Ledger WL, Li TC. Does high body mass index increase the risk of miscarriage after spontaneous and assisted conception? A meta-analysis of the evidence. *Fertil Steril*, 2010; 94(3): 714-726.
35. Lashen H, Fear K, Sturdee DW. Obesity is associated with increased risk of first trimester and recurrent miscarriage: matched case-control study. *Hum Reprod*, 2004; 19(7): 1644-1646.
36. Palomba S, de Wilde MA, Falbo A, Koster MP. The risk of a persistent ectopic pregnancy after linear salpingostomy for a tubal pregnancy in women with a prior salpingostomy or salpingectomy: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Obstet Gynaecol*, 2015; 122(8): 991-997,
37. Rotterdam ESHRE/ASRM-Sponsored PCOS Consensus Workshop Group. Revised 2003 consensus on diagnostic criteria and long-term health risks related to polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). *Hum Reprod*, 2004; 19(1): 41-47.
38. Cedergren MI. Maternal morbid obesity and the risk of adverse pregnancy outcome. *Obstet Gynaecol*, 2004; 103(2): 219-224,
39. Chu SY, Callaghan WM., Kim SY, Schmid CH, Lau J, England LJ, Dietz PM. Maternal obesity and risk of gestational diabetes mellitus. *Diabetes Care*, 2007; 30(8): 2070-2076.
40. Stothard KJ, Tennant PW, Bell R, Rankin J. Maternal overweight and obesity and the risk of congenital anomalies: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA*, 2009; 301(6): 636-650,
41. Baeten JM, Bukusi EA, Lambe M. Pregnancy complications and outcomes among overweight and obese nulliparous women. *Am J Publ Health*, 2001; 91(3): 436-440.
42. Regan L, Rai R. Epidemiology, and the medical causes of miscarriage. *Baillieres Best Pract Res Clin Obst Gynaecol*, 2000; 14(5): 839-854.
43. Pasquali R, Pelusi C, Gambineri A. Obesity and reproductive disorders in women. *Hum Reprod Update*, 2007; 13(4): 395-404.
44. Diamanti-Kandarakis E, Dunaif A. Insulin resistance and the polycystic ovary syndrome revisited: an update on mechanisms and implications. *Endocrine Rev*, 2012, 33(6): 981-1030.
45. Bellver J, Pellicer A. Obesity and assisted reproductive technology outcomes. *Reprod Biomed Online*, 2011; 23(6): 720-728.
46. Kaaks R, Lukanova A, Kurzer MS. Obesity, endogenous hormones, and endometrial cancer risk: a synthetic review. *CEBP*, 2002; 11(12): 1531-1543.

47. Subak LL, Richter HE, Hunskaar S. Obesity and urinary incontinence: epidemiology and clinical research update. *J Urol*, 2008; 180(1): 27-37.
48. Clapp MA, Little SE, Zheng J, Robinson JN. A multi-state analysis of post-operative adverse events in 762,239 gynecologic surgical admissions for benign indications. *J Minim Invasive Gynaecol*, 2018; 25(2): 296-302.
49. Bajos N, Wellings K, Laborde C, Moreau C. Sexuality and obesity, a gender perspective: results from French national random probability survey of sexual behaviours. *BMJ*, 2010; 340: c2573.
50. Griffiths LJ, Parsons TJ, Hill AJ. Self-esteem and quality of life in obese children and adolescents: a systematic review. *Int J Pediatr Obesity*, 2010; 5(4): 282-304.
51. Stovall DW, Allen R, Khardori R, Lebovic DI. Epigenetics and gynaecologic disease: the promise of targeted therapy. *J Minim Invasive Gynaecol*, 2016; 23(2): 307-318.
52. Dietz PM, England LJ, Callaghan WM, Pearl M, Wier ML, Kharrazi M. A comparison of LMP-based and ultrasound-based estimates of gestational age using linked California livebirth and prenatal screening records. *Pediatr Perinatal Epidemiol*, 2007; 21(Suppl 2): 62-71.
53. Teede HJ, Misso ML, Costello MF, Dokras A, Laven J, Moran L, Norman RJ. Recommendations from the international evidence-based guideline for the assessment and management of polycystic ovary syndrome. *Clin Endocrinol*, 2018; 89(3): 251-268.
54. Nayak L, Sahu BP. A review on herbal medicine and health. *J Pharm Adv Res*, 2018; 1(1): 1-7.